

Supplementary Material of: Analysis of self-reported discard information in Uruguayan industrial trawl fisheries

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Table 1. Mean and standard deviation of yearly aggregated haul data for: Shannon’s diversity index (H’), species richness(S) and Pielou’s evenness (J) for shelf and coastal fleets discarded catch.

	year	H'	S	J
shelf fleet	2016	1.72 ± 0.33	14.00 ± 1.54	0.65 ± 0.12
	2017	1.94 ± 0.12	14.50 ± 0.93	0.73 ± 0.02
	2019	1.39 ± 0.20	17.50 ± 0.75	0.50 ± 0.09
	2020	1.11 ± 0.26	15.25 ± 0.49	0.41 ± 0.08
coastal fleet	2016	0.96 ± 0.33	12.00 ± 3.46	0.39 ± 0.14
	2017	1.39 ± 0.22	13.25 ± 0.5	0.54 ± 0.09
	2019	1.46 ± 0.29	16.00 ± 4.89	0.54 ± 0.08
	2020	1.63 ± 0.27	14.25 ± 2.06	0.62 ± 0.09

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation of seasonally aggregated haul data for: Shannon’s diversity index (H’), species richness(S) and Pielou’s evenness (J) for shelf and coastal fleets discarded catch .

	season	H'	S	J
shelf fleet	Summer	1.76 ± 0.35	15.00 ± 1.41	0.65 ± 0.14
	Autum	1.41 ± 0.41	14.00 ± 0.82	0.53 ± 0.15
	Winter	1.35 ± 0.45	16.50 ± 6.35	0.50 ± 0.19
	Spring	1.64 ± 0.35	15.75 ± 1.26	0.60 ± 0.14
coastal fleet	Summer	1.34 ± 0.31	12.25 ± 3.59	0.54 ± 0.08
	Autum	1.64 ± 0.33	14.50 ± 1.29	0.62 ± 0.13
	Winter	1.14 ± 0.43	13.00 ± 2.94	0.44 ± 0.14
	Spring	1.32 ± 0.29	15.75 ± 4.35	0.49 ± 0.11